

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B436
 Date: 21 Apr 2009
 Take Off: 09:46:36Z
 Landing: 14:25:28Z
 Flight Time 4h 40m 52s

Campaign: MEVEX (Dust)
Operating Area: Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Jon Taylor	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
13	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	NCAS Leeds	
14	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
15	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
16	Observer	Dave Membury	Met Office	
17	Observer	Said Al Harami	Oman Dept Meteorology	
18	Observer	Hamed	Oman Dept Meteorology	
19	Observer	Sgt Sami Al Fulaimani	National Survey of Oman	

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_100530_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_110530_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_120530_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_130530_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_140530_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_130519_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_140519_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_100519_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_110519_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_120519_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_100525_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_110525_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_120525_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_130525_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_140525_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

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Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
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 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_140530_1hz.avi

 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_100519_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_110519_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090421_r0_b436_120519_1hz.avi

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No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B436
 Date: 21 April 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
085534		!	0.18 kft	308	start CPC recording
092428		Start-Up	0.19 kft	308	
093118		!	0.19 kft	308	start taxi
093132		!	0.19 kft	308	open ASPs
093618		!	0.19 kft	308	start pirouette
093915		!	0.20 kft	308	end pirouette
094636		T/O	0.0 kft	308	from Muscat
095512		!	13.1 kft	308	retract BBR
095652		!	15.5 kft	308	Nevzorov/JW zero
100338		!	23.4 kft	308	Heimann cal
100547		Video	24.0 kft	308	start recording
110206	110405	Orbit 1	24.1 - 24.0 kft	070	
110450	110650	Orbit 2	24.0 kft	131	
110831	114331	Run 1	24.0 kft	031	
111237		!	24.0 kft	027	Heimann cal
111409		!	24.0 kft	027	Nevzorov/JW zero
113429		!	24.0 kft	000	Nevzorov/JW zero
114328		!	24.0 kft	018	Nevzorov/JW zero
114349	114531	Orbit 3	24.1 - 24.0 kft	043	
114835	120056	Profile 1	24.1 - 14.0 kft	197	
115242		!	20.6 kft	209	Nevzorov zero
115738		!	15.8 kft	208	General Eastern switched to zero (fault clearance)
120217	121719	Run 2	14.1 - 14.0 kft	002	
121101		!	14.0 kft	019	Heimann cal
121949	122517	Profile 2	14.0 - 9.1 kft	201	
122656	124156	Run 3	9.2 kft	002	
122821		!	9.2 kft	009	Heimann cal
124423	125446	Profile 3	9.2 - 0.38 kft	214	
125500	130524	Run 4	0.31 - 0.27 kft	205	
125500				205	Heimann cal
130737	130832	Orbit 4	0.75 - 0.74 kft	081	
130921	131032	Orbit 5	0.72 - 0.76 kft	283	
131525		!	2.1 kft	200	Heimann cal
131917	132321	Run 5	2.1 kft	281	
132349	132448	Profile 4	1.6 - 1.0 kft	280	
132506	133059	Run 6	0.99 - 1.1 kft	279	
134234		!	20.0 kft	207	Heimann cal
134452	135148	Run 7	20.0 kft	301	

135243	141435	Run 8	20.0 - 18.5 kft	350
142528		Land	0.20 kft	266 at Muscat

B436 06:23:40-14:38:40

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

OOMS -> OMDB - Overview

NavData Cycle 2009-4 Expires: Thursday, 07 May 2009.

Scale: 1:2047666 (1 inch = 28.08 naut mi). Printed on 20 Apr 2009

7 6 9 9 6 ; 6 8

FliteStar 9.4.5.0

MEVEX – Aerosol and Land Surface Emissivity Sortie – B436

Date: 21st April 2009

Mission Scientist: *Jonathan Arnold*

T/O OOMS: 09:15Z (13:15 local)

Land OOMS: 13:25Z (17:25 local)

Location: West coast of Oman and Ramlat Al Wahibah – Oman Low Level Flying Area 1.

Weather: Cloud free conditions

Sortie Aim: To validate forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions and the IR and microwave surface emissivity of desert surfaces coordinated with an IASI overpass.

Key Instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, SID 3, AVAPS, Neph

Sortie profile:

Item No.	Detail	Item time	Running time	Local time
1	Take off OOMS		09:15:00	13:15:00
2	Transit to operating area	00:50:00	10:05:00	14:05:00
3	Two orbits at bank angle to be defined by mission scientist	00:05:00	10:10:00	14:10:00
4	Fly straight and level run at FL240	00:35:00	10:45:00	14:45:00
5	Two orbits at bank angle to be defined by mission scientist	00:05:00	10:50:00	14:50:00
6	Profile descent to FL150 or other suitable level	00:10:00	11:00:00	15:00:00
7	Straight and level run at FL150	00:15:00	11:15:00	15:15:00
8	Profile descent to FL50 or other suitable level	00:10:00	11:25:00	15:25:00
9	Straight and level run at FL50	00:15:00	11:40:00	15:40:00
10	Profile descent to 100 ft	00:10:00	11:50:00	15:50:00
11	Straight and level run at 100 ft	00:10:00	12:00:00	16:00:00
12	Two orbits at bank angle to be defined by mission scientist	00:05:00	12:05:00	16:05:00
13	Straight and level run at min alt crossing coast in Low level area 1	00:10:00	12:15:00	16:15:00
14	Profile ascent to max alt at 1000 ft/min interrupting to remain in area above item 13	00:30:00	12:45:00	16:45:00
15	Fly two SLRs at max alt aligned with item 13 dropping 2 sondes	00:20:00	13:05:00	17:05:00
16	Recover to OOMS	00:20:00	13:25:00	17:25:00
	Total sortie time		04:10:00	04:10:00

INSTS: PCASP + Neph on from PNE T/O to landing.

TRANSITS: Lidar, ARIES $\downarrow \uparrow$, SWS $\downarrow$ and $\uparrow$ coordinate

RF - ARIES $\downarrow \uparrow$ SWS same. LIDAR = $\checkmark$ => need height details of layers + gradients

6 FL150 or? - Filters, ARIES help $\uparrow$ help $\downarrow$ SWS same; Lidar on

PCASP - Filters ARIES $\uparrow$ and $\downarrow$ SWS same - Lidar on.

100ft - Filters? TBA ARIES $\uparrow$ + ~~shot~~ $\downarrow$ Atmospheric SWS caps ARIES - no Lidar. (over sea.).

Max Alt - Lidar, ARIES $\downarrow$ shot $\uparrow$ 1 sock over land (over ocean SWS $\downarrow$ shot $\uparrow$)

MEVEX – Aerosol and Land Surface Emissivity Sortie – B436**Date:** 21st April 2009**Mission Scientist:****T/O OOMS:** 09:15Z (13:15 local)**Land OOMS:** 13:25Z (17:25 local)**Location:** West coast of Oman and Ramlat Al Wahibah – Oman Low Level Flying Area 1.**Weather:** Cloud free conditions**Sortie Aim:** To validate forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions and the IR and microwave surface emissivity of desert surfaces coordinated with an IASI overpass.**Key Instruments:** ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, SID 3, AVAPS, Neph**Sortie profile:**

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6	Profile descent to FL150 or other suitable level	00:10:00	11:00:00	15:00:00
7	Straight and level run at FL150	00:15:00	11:15:00	15:15:00
8	Profile descent to FL50 or other suitable level	00:10:00	11:25:00	15:25:00
9	Straight and level run at FL50	00:15:00	11:40:00	15:40:00
10	Profile descent to 100 ft	00:10:00	11:50:00	15:50:00
11	Straight and level run at 100 ft	00:10:00	12:00:00	16:00:00
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Mission Scientists Debrief – MEVEX Flight B436 21st April 2009.

Jonathan P. Taylor.

Summary

This was a very successful first flight for MEVEX. The Met Office CAM model had predicted a gradient in aerosol along the East coast of Oman with higher concentrations to the North. Aerosol optical depths at Muscat before take off were 0.6 at 0.5microns. Flight was focussed on studying a desert dust aerosol layer that extended from the surface to 18000ft. All instruments worked well. Analysis of lidar data in flight showed gradient in aerosol tops from 13000ft to South to 18000ft to North.

Detailed Report

A microtops measurement before take off gave the following optical depths:

340nm = 0.543
440nm = 0.579
500nm = 0.614
675nm = 0.584
1020nm = 0.513

Before take off a pirouette was performed on the pan for SWS scan and BBR checks. The profile out of Muscat showed aerosol concentrations around 200cm⁻³ on the PCASP. The top of the aerosol layer was at around 18000ft and was topped with broken cloud (~5 oktas). We then transited south to the operating area at FL240 and the lidar soon reported that all cloud has disappeared and there was now only aerosol below. As we headed south the lidar reported that the tops of the aerosol layer was decreasing in altitude with tops now near 15000ft. After crossing the coast two orbits were flown with the SWS looking down at the ocean through the aerosol layer. A straight and level run was then flown from south to north at FL240. Lidar reported aerosol tops at 13000ft at southern end of run and around 16000ft at northern end of run. At the northern end of the run a further orbit was flown over the aerosol layer before descending to FL140 for a 15 min run in the aerosol layer. PCASP concentrations were now reported at around 100cm⁻³, nephelometer showed clear distinction with red scattering more than green more than blue indicating dust. Scattering variable but around 100m⁻¹. Following a short profile a further run was flown at 9000ft in the aerosol layer on a reciprocal heading. PCASP concentrations were around 100cm⁻³, with large aerosol being seen by PCASP, FFSSP and CDP. A profile was then flown down to 100ft remaining in aerosol all the way to the surface. A run was then flown over the sea at 100ft with two 60 deg banked orbits at 600ft looking up through the aerosol. A run was then flown at 2000ft crossing from ocean to land. Once over land we descended to 900ft over the surface. There was considerable variation in the surface structure of the sand. At the beginning of the run the sand was arranged in small scale randomly orientated dunes which often had clumps of small scrub. Then the surface became dominated with large North-South oriented dunes of larger scale and significantly reduced vegetation and then changed again to fairly flat desert with small trees widely scattered. Following the low level runs a quick ascent to FL200 was made followed by a short run at this altitude back over the same land track as the low level run. The profile up over the land showed an

increased amount of aerosol in the lowest 5000ft with the aerosol tops at 17000ft.
During the run at FL200 a drop sonde was launched.

Picture 1 = desert typical of start of low level run

Picture 2 – desert typical of middle of run

Picture 3 – desert typical of end of run

Aerol Mass = 1.092
 SPCON = 1.011

MEVEX

ON GROUND MICRONS

Aircraft Scientist's Log

0715 Z

340 = 5.07E-01 675 = 7.56E+00 1020 = 0.513
 440 = 7.46E+00 1020 = 4.03E+00
 500 = 8.33E+00 $\theta = 23.766^\circ$

340nm = 0.543
 440nm = 0.579
 500nm = 0.614
 675 = 0.584

Flight No **B.436**

Date 21/4/09

Page 1 of 4

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					067 Feet from SA CAM CAM
					007 on 21/4/09
					has AOD $\approx$ 0.8 to 1.6. aer Muscat
					067 COMPS run 127 on 19/4
					Int optical depth $\approx$ 0.2 to 0.4 near Muscat
093618		ON GROUND			Start of promette SWS = 28°
093915					End of promette. $\theta = 24.7^\circ$
					PCASP $\approx$ 200 cm ⁻³
094936					TO $\approx$ base peak in night at 2800ft $\approx$ 1500m
					visibility is very poor lets go back
					no clear horizon.
					below $\approx$ 19000ft night and $\approx$ 80 m ⁻¹ $\approx$ 278 ish.
095637	FL150				cloud at top of b'dy base
095912	FL188				Above all cloud now $\approx$ 5/8 cover
					clear skies above.
					new PCASP nearby channel 1.
					LWIR OK.
103605	FL240			T-16	Under engine all aerosol below.
				Td = 35.	bps decreasing in altitude $\approx$ 2800m below.
104008	FL240			T = -16 Td = -61	Heading close to 122 deg. now
					landing trends coast under reports
					tips of aerosol layer decreasing.
					Under sees thick layer 2800m below us.
					$\approx$ 1000ft thick

MEVEX

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Son Tarcen

Flight No **B** 436
FAAM © 2004

Date 21/4/09

Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
110 00 ²⁶		FL240			St abt 1 Bank = 45°
					E abt 1 $\theta = 43^\circ$
110450					S abt 2
110650		FL240			E abt 2
110831	R1	FL240	023		Sty Perm 1 T = -16 Td = -35 dB winds 19 kts / 302 deg Ald pres above + below.
111450					lower reports 3450m to tops of base 4450m below us.
113335					lower flows across layer thin + less dense as we hd north east clouds over head ahead but clear seen.
114331	R1	FL240	018	21°48'N 60°E.	End of Perm. 1
114349	03	FL240			5 03 50°
114531	03	FL240			End 03 50° Ring down $\theta = 55^\circ$
114835	PLV	FL240	201	21°30' 60°E	Sty PLV 2 1000 ft/min. tops of ans l = FL155 winds 270 at top of perm but now 318 deg in record layer Neph RGB all same = 38 → 65 m!

3450*
+ 13
= 350

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MEVEX

J. TAYLOR

Flight No **B** 436
FAAM © 2004

Date 21/4/09

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1202A	R2	FL140	005		Stg Run 2 - wind 13m/s 336° T = -1.5k Td = -6.5
121320					Wash temp G B = 100 G 115 when impacts off, B - 130 m ⁻¹ ie seeing large dust with
					PCASP ≈ 80/cc but constant on run constant.
121949	P2↓	9000ft	203		Stg P2 in aerosol layer Wash
12251A	P2	9000ft			End of P2
122656	P3	9000ft	003		Stg Run 3 in aerosol layer T = 12.3 Td = -7.5 wind 006m/s / 303° R ≈ 50 - 110 m ⁻¹ G ≈ 20 → 60 m ⁻¹ B ≈ 20 → 100 m ⁻¹ PCASP ≈ 80 → 100/cc SIP3 stopped PCASP seeing 3µm aerosol during run but below CDPT FFSSP seeing some pbls to deposit
124156	P3	9000ft			End of Run 3
124423	P3↓	9000ft 2500ft	212		Stg P3 down to 1000ft in aerosol layer wind 10m/s at 210deg Top of MBL ≈ 1340ft
125500	P3	1000ft			End of P3

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MEVEX

Jan Taylor

Flight No **B.436**
FAAM © 2004

Date 21/6/09

Page 4 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
125500	R4	100ft.			st Run 4 up to 100ft T = 29.8 Td = 20.3°C Wind 12 m/s 202 deg SST ≈ 26.4°C. Weghs now Bhe > G > Red + deepens. ≈ 90, 80, 75 m ⁻¹ .
130524	R4	100ft	208	21°30' 59°30'	End of Run 4
130737	O4	60ft			stg O4 60° bend D = 73°
130842					End of O4
130921	O5	60ft			stg O5
131037	O5	60ft			End of O5
131917	R5	200ft	280	21°12' 59°18'	stg Run 5 over sea to cross coast
132306	R5	200ft			Over coast
132759 132828	R4	200ft	280		stg R4 some patches of veg shelter chase in sand large & dense + no veg
					★ R6 132506 → 133059 at 90ft Fast climb at 200ft/min to FE200 top of cloud 17500ft. on 1013
		FE200	110		Drop of sand 1.
134452	R7	FE200	298		stg R7. over desert BRIES ↓ low on mt clouds at 100ft above all aerrd old ahead on top of dust layer
135148	R7	FE200			End R7.

135263
135824

over cloud

st R8 over sea

```
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 21/04/2009 11:33:10
[2009/04/21 11:33] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.208) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/21 11:33] *** Mode change [+nt] on #mevex by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
[2009/04/21 11:38] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.39) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/21 11:39] <FAAM> contact....
[2009/04/21 11:40] <FAAM> calling Ted@base ops
[2009/04/21 11:41] <FAAM> calling.....
[2009/04/21 11:43] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.39) has quit IRC [Quit: Client exited]
[2009/04/21 11:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] How is it going?
[2009/04/21 12:04] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.39) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/21 12:04] [FAAMOpsDetach] Hello
[2009/04/21 12:05] <FAAM> finally! Wot time do u call this then?
[2009/04/21 12:06] [FAAMOpsDetach] Ted asks, is there any dust?
[2009/04/21 12:06] <FAAM> yes. Do u have the sortie brief 2 hand?
[2009/04/21 12:07] [FAAMOpsDetach] nearly
[2009/04/21 12:07] [FAAMOpsDetach] got it
[2009/04/21 12:07] <FAAM> well if u did, I could tell you that we are on item7
[2009/04/21 12:08] [FAAMOpsDetach] Okay, so working your way down to low level
[2009/04/21 12:08] <FAAM> 10:4
[2009/04/21 12:08] [FAAMOpsDetach] Any snagettes?
[2009/04/21 12:09] <FAAM> we are having to alter our plans...short of fuel
[2009/04/21 12:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] ETA?
[2009/04/21 12:09] <FAAM> GIN ok
[2009/04/21 12:09] <FAAM> not yet
[2009/04/21 12:09] <FAAM> TDLAS seems ok
[2009/04/21 12:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] when did it spring into life?
[2009/04/21 12:10] <FAAM> Gen Eastern threw a wobbler at hi level, ok after switch to zero
[2009/04/21 12:10] <FAAM> after about 1 hour airborne
[2009/04/21 12:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] All our guests okay?
[2009/04/21 12:11] <FAAM> yes, all ok. Taking up too much room though, rear core console fully
    taken over
[2009/04/21 12:13] <FAAM> Nev v noisy, BTW: especially liquid water
[2009/04/21 12:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] Is the fuel thing just because you are so heavy (thats the
    communal you)?
[2009/04/21 12:13] <FAAM> not sure
[2009/04/21 12:15] <FAAM> separation of colours on neph: greater separation, smaller particles?
[2009/04/21 12:21] [FAAMOpsDetach] I think a greater range of sizes
[2009/04/21 12:21] <FAAM> ok
[2009/04/21 12:22] [FAAMOpsDetach] so, doesn't sound like it's going to badly, all things
    considered
[2009/04/21 12:22] [FAAMOpsDetach] We were planning to have a short meeting back at the hotel at
    2000L but that could come forward if you are coming back early
[2009/04/21 12:23] <FAAM> no, ok. turns out that the cyclone impactor was on the dry neph, the
    greater range was apparent with impactor removed
[2009/04/21 12:24] <FAAM> will let you know about eta etc
[2009/04/21 12:30] [FAAMOpsDetach] no flight tomorrow, pos fly thurs and fri
[2009/04/21 12:30] <FAAM> ok. The iR camera bay makes a considerable racket
[2009/04/21 12:37] <FAAM> problem with flight plan: time estimates crap
[2009/04/21 12:37] <FAAM> close to starting item 10
[2009/04/21 12:46] <FAAM> still there?
[2009/04/21 12:48] [FAAMOpsDetach] yes
[2009/04/21 12:49] [FAAMOpsDetach] Can you pass to Martin, shims cal tomorrow around 1700L
[2009/04/21 13:00] <FAAM> in the 100ft run at the moment
[2009/04/21 13:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] what's the sea temperature reading?
[2009/04/21 13:01] <FAAM> 26.5
[2009/04/21 13:04] <FAAM> flying over Dhows
[2009/04/21 13:08] [FAAMOpsDetach] coool
[2009/04/21 13:10] [FAAMOpsDetach] ETA yet?
[2009/04/21 13:18] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.39) has quit IRC
[2009/04/21 13:20] *** FAAM (~GLUXE@203.38.13.39) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/21 13:21] <FAAM> back.
[2009/04/21 13:24] [FAAMOpsDetach] how is the temperature in the cabin?
[2009/04/21 13:25] <FAAM> ok! Just over the desert now.....
[2009/04/21 13:27] [FAAMOpsDetach] any camels?
[2009/04/21 13:30] <FAAM> not yet... wild country though!
[2009/04/21 13:36] [FAAMOpsDetach] If anyone needs the toolkit post flight, the key is in the very
    front pocket of the p/f bag
[2009/04/21 13:37] [FAAMOpsDetach] Also, can someone have a look at the spare red bbr in the store
    and note its serial no. please?
[2009/04/21 13:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] the upper red fit for B435 doesn't agree with whats in the
    instrument calibration spreadsheet
[2009/04/21 13:55] [FAAMOpsDetach] Can you let Said know that his wife called to ask how he was.
    Also, can he call her after landing please?
[2009/04/21 13:55] [FAAMOpsDetach] ETA?
[2009/04/21 13:56] <FAAM> will do re Said
```

[2009/04/21 13:56] [FAAMOpsDetach] thank
[2009/04/21 13:57] <FAAM> eta 1425
[2009/04/21 13:58] <FAAM> pls pass on
[2009/04/21 13:58] <FAAM> and confirm receipt
[2009/04/21 14:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] eta passed on to ops 'n engs.
[2009/04/21 14:01] [FAAMOpsDetach] do you have enough transport to get everyone back?
[2009/04/21 14:01] <FAAM> who is meeting us at airport?
[2009/04/21 14:01] <FAAM> don't know
[2009/04/21 14:05] [FAAMOpsDetach] I'll come out and Dave K will to
[2009/04/21 14:07] <FAAM> good, I think that's sensible
[2009/04/21 14:07] [FAAMOpsDetach] heading off now see y'all out there
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 21/04/2009 14:07:49

Cloud Physics Flight Log B436

Date:21/04/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time:07:45:00	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	AUX1 Time:+0	AUX2 Time:+0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y		Y		Y	
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.8	Ref V (~3):	1.75	Vref (>7):	unknown	El#1 V (>1):	-1.75V	Ref V:	3.5V	Comms?	Yes
	Sample flow	1.3			Flow (~1):	0.62	El#32 V (>1):	-2.0V				
	Sheath flow	17.5			Pressure:	1013						
					Temp (NDIT)	40.1						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
11:02:05	FL240	0		Noise		25	0.06				45	0	Start Orbits
11:06:51													End of Orbits
11:08:30	FL240												Start Run 1
11:09:00		0		90	0.1	35	0.06					0	
11:11:00		0		100	0.1	30	0.06					0	
11:13:00		0		130	0.1	35	0.06					0	
11:15:00		0		150	0.1	50	0.06					0	
11:17:00		0		140	0.1	40	0.06					0	
11:19:00		0		150	0.1	70	0.06					0	
11:21:00		0		120	0.1	80	0.06					0	
11:23:00		0		120	0.1	80	0.06					0	
11:25:00		0		90	0.1	Noise						0	
11:27:00		0		130	0.1	Noise						0	
11:29:00		0		140	0.1	Noise						0	
11:31:00		0		140	0.1	Noise						0	
11:33:00		0		140	0.1	Noise						0	
11:35:00		0		140	0.1	Noise						0	
11:37:00		0		Noise		Noise						0	
11:39:00		0		Noise		Noise						0	
11:41:00		0		Noise		Noise						0	
11:43:32													End of Run
11:43:51	FL240	0		Noise		Noise						0	Start Orbits
11:45:37												Fail	End Orbits

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
11:48:39	FL240	0		Noise		25	0.06				45	Fail	Start Profile 1
11:49:53	FL230	0		Noise		75	0.06					Fail	
11:51:07	FL220	0		Noise		60	0.06					Fail	
11:52:19	FL210	0		Noise		40	0.06					Fail	
11:53:14	FL200	0		Noise		25	0.07					Fail	
11:54:10	FL190	0		Noise		55	0.07				46	Fail	
11:54:59	FL180	0		Noise		20	0.07					Fail	
11:56:01	FL170	0		Noise		45	0.07					Fail	
11:57:24	FL160	0.1	8	Noise		80	0.10					Fail	
11:58:28	FL150	0.3	4	Noise		80	0.12					Fail	
11:59:50	FL140	0.3	10	Noise		140	0.11					Fail	End of Profile
12:02:17	FL140												Start Run 2
12:03:00		0.4	10	Noise		80	0.14				47	Fail	
12:05:00		0.4	12	Noise		80	0.14				48	Fail	
12:07:00		0.4	12	Noise		80	0.14				49	Fail	
12:09:00		0.4	12	400	1.9	90	0.14				50	Fail	
12:11:00		0.4	12	400	1.8	90	0.12					Fail	
12:13:00		0.5	10	490	2.0	80	0.13				51	Fail	
12:15:00		0.6	10	480	1.7	85	0.13				52	Fail	
12:17:27													End of Run
12:19:48	FL140												Start Profile 2
12:20:57	FL130	0.6	10	500	2.0	90	0.13				54	Fail	
12:22:04	FL120	0.6	10	500	2.0	100	0.14					Fail	
12:23:07	FL110	0.6	10	500	2.0	110	0.12				55	Fail	
12:24:09	FL100	0.8	10	Noise		120	0.15					Fail	
12:25:07	FL090												End of Profile
12:26:56	FL090												Start Run 3
12:27:00		0.8	10	Noise		100	0.14				57	Fail	
12:29:00		0.8	10	Noise		90	0.13				58	Fail	
12:31:00		0.8	12	Noise		90	0.13				59	70	
12:33:00		0.8	12	Noise		90	0.13				60	70	
12:35:00		0.8	12	Noise		85	0.12				61	70	
12:37:00		0.8	10	Noise		90	0.12					70	
12:39:00		0.8	10	450	2.5	100	0.13				62	200	SID3 gains to 100
12:41:36													End of run
12:44:25	FL090												Start Profile 3

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
12:45:	FL080	0.8	10	500	2.1	110	0.12				65	200	
12:46:41	FL070	0.8	10	500	2.2	110	0.12				65	200	
12:47:50	FL060	0.8	10	450	2.2	120	0.12				66	200	
12:48:50	FL050	0.8	8	Noise		120	0.12				66	200	
12:49:50	FL050	0.9	8	Noise		130	0.12				67	200	Heaters off
12:50:55	FL040	0.9	8	Noise		150	0.11					200	
12:52:27	FL020	0.8	8	500	2.2	260	0.09				68	200	
12:53:29	FL010	0.6	7	500	2.1	140	0.11					200	
12:55:00	100'												End of Profile & Start Run 4 @ 100'
12:56:00		0.5	8	400	2.2	150	0.10				69	200	
12:58:00		0.6	7	430	2.2	180	0.10				70	200	
13:00:00		0.5	7	450	2.25	190	0.10				71	200	SID 150 gains
13:02:00		0.5	7	450	2.25	200	0.09					800	
13:04:00		0.5	7	400	2.25	200	0.09				72	700	
13:05:28													End of Run
13:07:36													Start Orbit
13:10:37													End Orbits
13:19:07	2000'												Start Run 5
13:20:00		0.4	6	250	1.75	100	0.12				78	800	
13:22:00		0.3	8	275	1.75	100	0.11				79	700	
13:23:35													Descending
13:24:20	1000'	0.3	8	350	2.4	140	0.10				80	600	
13:24:48	900'												Run 6
13:25:00		0.3	8	350	2.25	130	0.11					800	
13:27:00		0.4	8	350	2	140	0.11					900	
13:29:00	1000'	0.3	8	350	2.2	130	0.12				82	800	
13:31:00													End of Run
13:33:00	FL070												Heaters on
13:44:02	FL200												Start Run 7
13:45:00		0		100	0.2	20	0.07				85	5	
13:47:00		0		100	0.2	20	0.07				85	5	
13:49:00		0		100	0.2	15	0.07					5	
13:51:00				140	0.2	20	0.07					5	
13:52:43	FL200												Start Run 8
13:53:00		0		200	0.2	30	0.07				85	5	
13:55:00		0		170	0.2	15	0.07					5	

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
13:57:00	FL240	0		100	0.25	20	0.06				85	5	
13:59:00		0		100	0.25	10	0.06					5	
14:01:00		0		150	0.3	10	0.06						Fail
14:03:00		0		150	0.2	5	0.06						Off
14:05:00		0		150	0.2	15	0.06						
14:07:00		0		Noise		20	0.06						
14:09:00		0		100	0.25	20	0.06						
14:11:00		0		100	0.2	30	0.06				86		
14:13:00		0		100	0.2	20	0.06						
14:14:05													End of Run

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	Unkown	At low level OK, but at higher levels remove channel 1
	Flow:	0.8	
2DC	EI#1:	-1.5	
	EI#32:	-1.3	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.9	
	Flow:	1.34	
CDP	Laser V:	3.91	
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.4	
SID 3	Laser V:	Off	
Rack Equipment	1.6BG		Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B436

Date:

21-04-2009

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
	B436-N1	----	----						Lab blank
Filters run 1	B436-N2	----	----	Bottom					Blanks
Filters run 1	B436-N3	----	----	Top					
Filters run 2	B436-N4	----	----	Bottom	12:03:50	12:17:21		56	FL 140
Filters run 2	B436-N5	----	----	Top	12:03:50	12:17:21		136	
Filters run 3	B436-N6	----	----	Bottom	12:27:23	12:41:56		120	
Filters run 3	B436-N7	----	----	Top	12:27:23	12:41:56		203	

Flight:

B436

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevezorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B436

Date: 21st April 2009

Instruments

Core chemistry: heat problems at start of flight

SID3 two periods where SID3 failed to operate

New PCASP reported noisy on channel 1

IR camera: short-wave camera continues not to be functional

CVI – no HORACE input

FWVS – receiving temperature from HORACE, not dew point

Aircraft

Forward SATCOM-H telephone ringing continuously, but nobody there!

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: ~~1/20~~ 2/4/09

Flight No: B 436

Pre-Flighter: PDR

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16" NOT COLLECTED
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	LEFT FOR CHEM OPERATOR
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	LEFT FOR CHEM OPERATOR
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	BUYER'S PC HAD BSOD INSERTED PC CATCHES ON THE CORCON SOCKET
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	NOT FITTED
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	RECVR FAULT - BUT ALL SEEMS OKAY
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom C	Checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT FITTED
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	DRY NEPH OPERATOR
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	NOT BEING RUN
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	NOT FITTED
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3876 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	Topped up DI

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	NOT FITTED
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	1/
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	1/
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	1/
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3786 CPC	Drained	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
<u>External Checks</u>				
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
47	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
48	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
49	<input type="checkbox"/>			
50	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
51	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
52	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
53	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 436 page 1 of 3

Date: 21/APP/09 Operator(s): S. ROGERS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: Orion MEVEX 4h east of GMT

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0650	Delayed	Airport					Power-up OK
	BST!						NB. Change time takes account of BST so give BST time when setting the clock! NB: Date/Time panel requires root password
085730	—	CH cal	CH	C	81	56!	CH cal. Note: C at ambient.
093046	—	CH cal	CH	O	81	59	CH cal
093211	—	Z	Z	O	81	59	Free running Z for pinsetter ^{Stop at cal}
093940	—	CH cal	CH	O	81	59	CH cal.
0948—	Takeoff						C cooling during climb
100451	FL240	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min macro Hot at takeoff?
102027	"	Z1min	Z	O	81	41	Z1min Over land
102222	"	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min
103512	"	Z1min	Z	O	81	41	Z1min
103711	"	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min Turn @ ~10.40
104910	"	Z1min	Z	O	80	41	Z1min
105058	"	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min Crossing the comp ~@1056
105705	"	CH cal	CH	O	81	41	CH cal.
105845	"	Z	Z	O	81	41	Free running Z for orbit ^{Stop at cal.}
110206	01						Right bank orbit
110412		CH cal	CH	O	81	41	CH cal - now in orbit 2
110532	02	Z	Z	O	81	41	Free running Z orbit ^{stop at cal}
110833	⁰¹ FL240	Z1min	Z	O	81	41	Z1min macro.
111022	"	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min Something's not right - 3 mins of CBS!!!
							Script locked up @ 99% (357/360) Abort!
111530	"	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min - that's better.
1121—	"	Z1min	Z	O	81	41	Z1min
112352	"	N3min	N	O	81	41	N3min
113852	"	CH cal	CH	O	81	41	CH cal
114347	03	Z	Z	O	81	41	Free running Z
114544	FL240	CH cal	CH	O	81	41	CH cal
114835	↓						

ARIES flight log

Flight: B 4 3 6 page 2 of 3

Date: _____ Operator(s): _____ Res: _____ Gain A: _____ B: _____
 Loc./Notes: _____

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
12 03 00	¹²² FL140		CH	0	81	30	CH cal.
12 04 24	"	240 x 1	Z	0	81	31	Z aborted halting to match SWS
12 05 -		240 x 1	N	0	81	31	N
12 08 01		240 x 1	Z	0	81	31	Z
12 09 12		cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
12 10 31		240 x 1	N	0	81	31	N
12 12 43	"	240 x 1	Z	0	81	31	Z
12 15 04		240 x 1	N	0	81	31	N
12 17 08	↓	cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
12 18 59		cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
12 24 31		cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
12 26 56	¹²³ 9000 ft	240 x 1	Z	0	81	31	Z
12 29 05		240 x 1	N	0	81	31	N
12 31 26		240 x 1	Z	0	81	31	Z
12 32 56		cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
12 34 21		240 x 1	N	0			N
12 36		240 x 1	Z	0	81	31	Z
12 38 42		240 x 1	N	0	81	32	N
12 40 46	↓	cal	CH	0	81	31	CH cal.
	^{gross down} L 1000 ft						
12 54 10		cal	CH	0	81	32	CH cal.
12 55 32		240 x 1	Z	0	81	32	Z
12 57 24		240 x 1	N	0	81	33	N How is ambient T > CBB? See surface 26:4T
12 58 48		240 x 1	Z	0	81	34	Z
13 00 51		cal	CH	0	81	35	CH cal.
13 02 11		360 x 1	Z	0	81	35	Z
13 05 44		cal	CH	0	81	36	CH cal.
13 07 25	^{50 ft + 5} 6000 ft	Z	Z	0	81	38	Z free run way for orbit 60°
13 10 37		cal	CH	0	81	39	CH cal. ↳ stop for cal.
13 13 -	2000 ft	Z 1000	Z	0	81	40	Z 1000 meters.
13 22 40		N 360 x 1					Glitch (operator glitch!)

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	21/4/09	Flight	B436	log pages
Operator(s)	J. Bowles		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure	Muscat		Arrival	Muscat		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	Y					•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					06:00
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	?°C	Ch	?°C	Ch18	?°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					06:19
Initial target temperatures	Hot	310	Cold	318		
Target heating	Y					•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***	Y					•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					06:22
Scan indication	Monitor	Y	Visual	Y		

↓↓

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor		Visual			
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	09:00:00		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	313.9	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	39	31.4	32.88	38.59	33.75	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					
						09:29

Double 'Dry' Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B. B436**

 Date 21/04/09

 Operator's name: A. Wilson

 Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run	Height	Cyclone On?	Inlet RH	Dry neph flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph flow	Wet neph RH	Remark :
0650	00Z						15		WET NEPH (WN) Preflight OK
0720	00Z		DRY				20		DRY NEPH (DN) Preflight OK
1006	51Z	TRANSIT FL240		0.7	15	2.0	15	2	in TRANSIT : All OK.
1060	00Z				19.1		15		test the cyclone
1046	00Z				11.7		15		- " -
1054	00Z				16.8		15		- " -
1102	06Z	ORBIT 1 FL240		0	17.2	0	15	0	start orbit 1 45° Right wing down
1104	05Z	- " -			17.5		15		end orbit 1
1104	50Z	ORBIT 2			17.3		15		start orbit 2 - " -
1106	50Z	- " -			17.3		15		end " - 2
1108	31Z	R1 FL240		0	17.2	0	15	0	start R1
1111	30	- " -		0	16.4	0	15	0	
1121	20	R1 FL240			20.0		15		Adjust cyclone flow
1127	30				10.9		15		- " -
1142	00	FL240			17		15		- " -
1143	49	ORBIT 3 FL240			17.3		15		start orbit 3 50 AOB
1145	31	- " -							end orbit
1148	38	P1 FL240 ↓			16.3		15		start P1 & FL120
1159	30	P1 140			20		15		in P1 FL140

Flight B436 12:57:03

Heading 206 deg Speed 214 knots Height 0.2kft Press 1002mb

Lat 22°0.0'N Long 59°48.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 201 deg

Temp 29.92C Dewpoint 20.5C

From 11:45:47 to now

Current values		
+++++ STATIC PRESSURE	1002.71	mb
----- DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	29.92	deg C
----- DEW POINT	20.5	deg C

Flight B436 10:28:53

Heading 209 deg Speed 330 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb

Lat 20°54.0'N Long 56°42.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 255 deg

Temp -15.92C Dewpoint -38.83C

From 09:23:27 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	392.42	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-15.92	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-38.83	deg C

T/O :

Flight B436 13:47:08

Heading 297 deg Speed 305 knots Height 19.9kft Press 465mb

Lat 21°18.0'N Long 58°42.0'E Wind 25 ms-1/ 283 deg

Temp -7.66C Dewpoint -46.67C

From 13:08:47 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	465.65	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-7.67	deg C
-----	DEW POINT	-46.67	deg C

Page 1 TSM

Flight B436 10:28:19

Heading 210 deg Speed 329 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb

Lat 20°54.0'N Long 56°42.0'E Wind 13 ms-1/ 255 deg

Temp -15.88C Dewpoint -39.08C

From 09:46:47 to now

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	24.02	Kft
.....	NEPH BLUE SP	-0.72	m-1
.....	NEPH GREEN SP	0.18	m-1
.....	NEPH RED SP	0.79	m-1

● All
○
○
○

Flight B436 12:57:53

Heading 207 deg Speed 220 knots Height 0.2kft Press 1002mb

Lat 21°54.0'N Long 59°42.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 201 deg

Temp 29.73C Dewpoint 21.17C

From 11:45:47 to now

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.28	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
-----	NEPH BLUE SP	85.09	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
-----	NEPH GREEN SP	91.52	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
-----	NEPH RED SP	85.06	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

New plot, same times

Flight B436 12:40:22

Heading 10 deg Speed 245 knots Height 9.1kft Press 719mb

Lat 22°36.0'N Long 60°6.0'E Wind 7 ms-1/ 286 deg

Temp 11.86C Dewpoint -3.81C

From 11:48:47 to now

Current values		
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	45621 secs
—	NEPH BLUE SP	75.24 m-1
—	NEPH GREEN SP	76.39 m-1
—	NEPH RED SP	79.14 m-1

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+009

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 12Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+012

Southern Asia CAM Specific humidity
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

Specific humidity (leg1) T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

700hPa Dust concentration T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

850hPa Dust concentration T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

Surface Dust concentration T+009

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

Dust concentration (leg1) T+009

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 09Z on 21/04/2009, from 00Z on 21/04/2009

AOD T+009

Flight B436 13:46:34

Heading 302 deg Speed 295 knots Height 20.0kft Press 465mb

Lat 21°18.0'N Long 58°48.0'E Wind 22 ms-1/ 281 deg

Temp -9.19C Dewpoint -46.51C

From 13:08:47 to now

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	20.01	Kft	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
	NEPH BLUE SP	2.49	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
	NEPH GREEN SP	0.46	m-1	<input type="radio"/>
	NEPH RED SP	-0.9	m-1	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B436 12:57:25

Heading 207 deg Speed 217 knots Height 0.2kft Press 1002mb

Lat 21°54.0'N Long 59°48.0'E Wind 12 ms-1/ 202 deg

Temp 29.77C Dewpoint 21.07C

From 11:45:47 to now

Current values			
-----	PRESSURE HEIGHT	0.28	Kft
-----	NEPH BLUE SP	98.36	m-1
-----	NEPH GREEN SP	93.37	m-1
-----	NEPH RED SP	92.48	m-1

New plot, same times

Flight B436 12:18:03

Heading 303 deg Speed 262 knots Height 14.0kft Press 594mb

Lat 22°6.0'N Long 60°6.0'E Wind 17 ms-1/ 318 deg

Temp -2.25C Dewpoint -6.18C

From 11:48:47 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	44280	secs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All
—	NEPH BLUE SP	47.9	m-1	<input type="checkbox"/>
—	NEPH GREEN SP	47.82	m-1	<input type="checkbox"/>
—	NEPH RED SP	41.43	m-1	<input type="checkbox"/>

New plot, same times

Flight B436 13:55:29

Heading 346 deg Speed 281 knots Height 19.9kft Press 465mb

Lat 21°48.0'N Long 58°24.0'E Wind 24 ms-1/ 272 deg

Temp -6.63C Dewpoint -47.52C

From 09:45:47 to now

Current values			
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	50127	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
— PRESSURE HEIGHT	19.99	Kft	<input type="radio"/>